

Crystal structure of dichloro[(*N*-phenylcarbamoyl)pyridine]bis(dimethylsulphoxide)ruthenium(II). A voltammetric study to monitor acid-base controlled *N,O* to *N,N* donor site switch over[†]

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Manuscript received 05 September 2016, accepted 14 September 2016

Abstract : Reaction between (*N*-phenylcarbamoyl)pyridine (HL¹) and [Ru^{II}(DMSO)₄Cl₂] in refluxing ethanol affords crystalline of [Ru^{II}(HL¹)(DMSO)₂Cl₂] with coordination by the bidentate ligand HL¹ in its neutral form (providing a pyridine and an amide *O* coordination), two DMSO molecules and two chloride ions. Notably, C–H···X (X = Cl, O) secondary interactions triggered by Ru^{II}-coordinated chloride and DMSO generate 1D chain and self-complementary dimeric tectons which lead to the formation of 1D chain. The presence of C–H···π interactions is also observed between 4-position C–H of one *N*-phenyl ring and π cloud of neighbouring *N*-phenyl ring. These secondary interactions lead to the formation of 1D supramolecular chain. Titration of 1 with stoichiometric amount of Et₃N and HClO₄ brings about reversible switch over of donor site of amide *O* to deprotonated amide *N* and vice versa.

Keywords : Pyridine amide ligand, ruthenium(II) complex, crystal structure, redox and absorption spectral properties, reversible switching of pyridine amide *O* to pyridine amide *N* coordination by acid-base, cyclic voltammetry.

Introduction

The properties of metal-ligand coordination compounds, whether in classical inorganic coordination complexes or in organometallic compounds or in bioinorganic model compounds, are determined in large measure by the nature of ligands bound to the metal ion¹. From the standpoint of synthetic coordination chemistry, focus is therefore placed on the design of chelating ligands whose metal-binding sites differ in the nature of the donor atom. There has been an explosion of growth in the coordination chemistry of pyridine/pyrazine amide ligands in both nonbiological and biological areas². Deprotonated pyridine amide groups usually coordinate via the nitrogen atom whereas coordination via oxygen is more frequent for neutral ligands². The anionic ligand is a strong σ-donor capable of stabilizing metal ions in high (≥3) oxidation states.

Catalytic oxygenation based on the redox of transi-

tion-metal complexes of redox-inactive and redox-active ligands is of importance from synthetic and biological viewpoints³. Smooth electron-transfer through reversible redox of transition-metal ions with redox-inactive ligands is required for an efficient catalytic cycle. Since ligand coordination greatly contributes to their redox processes, ligand design is essential in the construction of a versatile redox system. Conformationally flexible ligands are considered to permit us to construct an efficient catalytic system, rather than the rigid ones.

In the pursuit of economical and environmentally-friendly processes for the production of epoxides, the selective epoxidation of olefins with molecular oxygen is particularly desirable⁴. The epoxidation of cyclic alkenes with molecular oxygen was efficiently completed in excellent epoxide yield using a ruthenium(III) complex as catalyst, under mild reaction conditions⁵. The complex is *cis*-[Ru^{III}(HL¹)(L)Cl₂], where HL is *N*-2'-chlorophenyl-

[†]In honour of Professor Mahesh C. Chattopadhyaya.

2-pyridinecarboxamide and L is its corresponding anion⁵. The ruthenium(II) complexes of proposed composition dichloro[(*N*-phenylcarbamoyl)pyridine]bis(dimethylsulfoxide)ruthenium(II) $[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{HL})(\text{DMSO})_2\text{Cl}_2]$, with *cis*-DMSO and *trans*-dichloro coordination (Fig. 1), were used as catalysts for the epoxidation of olefins⁶. The complexes exhibited low-to-moderate catalytic activity. As for these ruthenium(II) complexes X-ray structural proof was missing, we aimed at crystallizing one of these complexes for structural authentication of its molecular structure. Herein we report on structural characterization of the unsubstituted complex (X = H) $[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{HL}^1)(\text{DMSO})_2\text{Cl}_2]$, crystallized as $[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{HL}^1)(\text{DMSO})_2\text{Cl}_2] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**1**), along with analysis of its crystal packing and its absorption spectroscopic and redox properties in acetonitrile.

Fig. 1. The complexes of pertinence to this work.

Experimental

Materials :

All reagents were obtained from commercial sources and used as received. Solvents were dried/purified as reported previously⁷. Tetra-*n*-butylammonium perchlorate (TBAP) was prepared and purified as before⁸. $[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{DMSO})_4\text{Cl}_2]$ was prepared following a reported procedure⁹. The ligand HL^1 was synthesized as before¹⁰.

Synthesis of complex :

$[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{HL}^1)(\text{DMSO})_2\text{Cl}_2] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**1**) : A mixture of solid $[\text{Ru}(\text{DMSO})_4\text{Cl}_2]$ (0.1 g, 0.21 mmol) and HL^1 (0.41 g, 0.21 mmol) was refluxed in ethanol (10 mL) for 1 h. The compound that precipitated out was filtered, washed with a mixture of ethanol-diethyl ether (1 : 5, v/v) and then dried in vacuum. Yield : 0.078 g, ~71%. Single-crystals suitable for X-ray diffraction were obtained by vapour-

diffusion of diethyl ether to an acetonitrile solution of the complex with composition $[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{HL}^1)(\text{DMSO})_2\text{Cl}_2] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**1**); Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{30}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_7\text{Ru}$ 598.1 : C, 32.10; H, 5.02; N, 4.68. Found : C, 31.95; H, 4.95; N, 4.50%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1} , selected peaks) : 3202 $\nu(\text{NH})$ and 1624, 1579 $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$; Absorption spectrum [λ_{max} , nm (ϵ , $\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)] (in acetonitrile) : 295 (800), 455 (27); ^1H NMR (CD_3CN , 500 MHz, peaks of coordinated HL^1) δ : 10.43 (1H, b, NH), 7.20–7.45 (1H, m.), 8.25 (1H, d), 7.87 (6H, t), 7.28 (1H, m).

Physical measurements :

Elemental analysis was obtained using Thermo Quest EA1110 CHNS-O, Italy. UV-Vis spectra were recorded at 298 K using an Agilent 8453 diode-array spectrophotometer. ^1H NMR spectrum (CD_3CN) was obtained on a JEOL JNM LA 500 (400 MHz) spectrometer. Chemical shifts are reported in ppm referenced to TMS.

Cyclic Voltammetric (CV) and Differential Pulse Voltammetric (DPV) experiments were performed at 298 K by using CH Instruments Electrochemical Analyzer/Workstation model 600B series. The cell contained a Beckman M-39273 platinum-inlay working electrode, a Pt wire auxiliary electrode, and a saturated calomel electrode (SCE), as reference electrode. Details of the cell configuration are as described before⁸.

Under our experimental conditions, the $E_{1/2}$ and peak-to-peak separation (ΔE_p) values in acetonitrile for $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2]^+ / [\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2]$ (Fc^+ / Fc) couple were 0.40 V vs SCE and 80 mV, respectively⁷.

X-Ray crystallography :

A single-crystal of suitable dimension was used for data collection. Diffracted intensities were collected on a Bruker SMART APEX CCD diffractometer, with graphite monochromated Mo-K α ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) radiation at 100(2) K. For data reduction the 'Bruker Saint Plus' program was used. Empirical absorption correction (SADABS) was applied to data sets. Structure was solved by SIR-97, expanded by Fourier-difference syntheses, and refined SHELXL-97, incorporated in WinGX 1.64 crystallographic package^{11a}. The positions of the hydrogen atoms associated with carbon atoms of the coordinated

ligand HL¹ were calculated assuming ideal geometries, but not refined. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic thermal parameters by full-matrix least-squares procedure on F^2 . After anisotropic refinement, an unassigned electron density peak of 3.91 eÅ⁻³ was found near Ru at a distance of 0.05 Å in the final difference Fourier map. Four water molecules were identified in the asymmetric unit. The hydrogen atoms of three such water molecules could not be identified/assigned. We could also not identify/assign the hydrogen atom of the carboxamide N–H. This must be due to the poor quality of crystal chosen for data collection. Unfortunately, we could not grow single crystals of the complex **1** that were any better than the one used for the present study. Pertinent crystallographic parameters are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Crystallographic data for [Ru(HL ¹)Cl ₂ (DMSO) ₂] \cdot 4H ₂ O	
Empirical formula	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₇ RuS ₂
Formula mass	591.45
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	$P2_1/c$
<i>a</i> (Å)	14.842(5)
<i>b</i> (Å)	21.452(5)
<i>c</i> (Å)	7.807(5)
α (deg)	90.00
β (deg)	99.799(5)
γ (deg)	90.00
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	2449.4(19)
<i>Z</i>	4
<i>D</i> _{Calcd.} (mg m ⁻³)	1.604
<i>T</i> (K)	100(2)
μ (mm ⁻¹)	1.066
<i>R</i> ₁ ^a	0.0680
<i>wR</i> ₂ ^b	0.1857
GOF	1.265
^a $R_1 = \sum F_o - F_c / \sum F_o $. ^b $wR_2 = \{\sum [w(F_o ^2 - F_c ^2)^2] / \sum [w(F_o ^2)^2]\}^{1/2}$.	

Intermolecular contacts of the C–H \cdots O, C–H \cdots Cl, and C–H \cdots π type were examined with the DIAMOND package^{11b}.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization :

A few comments regarding the synthesis of HL¹ are

in order. The formation of the ligand HL¹ was first reported as early as 1948^{12a}. Following a modified method reported^{12b} in 1978, we prepared and reported its synthesis in 1994¹⁰. For reasons unknown to us neither of these authors Bhattacharya and coworkers in 1999^{6a} nor Guo and coworkers in 2002^{13a} and Bhattacharya and coworkers in 2004^{13b}, cited our reference¹⁰ but Guo and coworkers^{13a} and Bhattacharya and coworkers^{13b}, cited Bhattacharya and coworkers^{6a}.

The synthesis and characterization of five Ru^{II} complexes with the pyridine amide ligand system of composition [Ru^{II}(HL)(DMSO)₂Cl₂] (Fig. 2) have been reported in the literature^{6a}. We prepared the air-stable complex [Ru^{II}(HL¹)(DMSO)₂Cl₂] in good yield (~70%) by refluxing the ruthenium precursor complex [Ru^{II}(DMSO)₄Cl₂]⁹ and the ligand HL¹ in ethanol, instead of methanol, as reported^{6a}. Single-crystals suitable for X-ray diffraction studies of composition [Ru^{II}(HL¹)(DMSO)₂Cl₂] \cdot 4H₂O (**1**) were obtained by vapour-diffusion of diethyl ether to an acetonitrile solution of the complex. Complex **1** is readily soluble in acetonitrile. Elemental analysis, IR (presence of -NH vibration indicates coordination by the neutral form of the ligand) and electronic spectral data of the complex are in excellent agreement with the reported data for complex **1**^{6a}.

In order to authenticate the structure of complex **1**, single-crystal X-ray crystallographic analysis has been done. Perspective view of the metal-coordination environment of complex [Ru^{II}(HL¹)(DMSO)₂Cl₂] \cdot 4H₂O (**1**) is shown in Fig. 1.

Selected bond distances and angles are collected in Table 2. Molecular structure of **1** reveals that a HL¹ ligand is coordinated by pyridine *N* and amide *O* donors (coordination in the neutral form), two dimethylsulphoxide molecules and two chlorides, coordinated to a ruthenium(II) in grossly octahedral geometry. Two DMSO molecules are coordinated in *cis*-positions and the chlorides are in the *trans*-positions. The angles between *trans* atoms at the Ru^{II} centre are N1–Ru–S1 167.61(15)°, O1–Ru–S2 177.00(13)° and Cl1–Ru–Cl2 173.72(6)°. The *cis*-angles span a wide range 76.85(19)° – 95.13(6)°. The S1–Ru–

Fig. 2. Perspective view of the metal-coordination unit of $[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{HL}^1)(\text{DMSO})_2\text{Cl}_2]\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**1**). Only donor atoms are labeled. All the hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity.

Table 2. Selected bond lengths (Å) and bond angles (deg) in $[\text{Ru}(\text{HL}^1)(\text{DMSO})_2\text{Cl}_2]\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Ru–N(1)	2.137(5)	N1–Ru–O1	6.85(19)
Ru–O(1)	2.118(4)	N1–Ru–Cl1	4.92(13)
Ru–S(1)	2.237(17)	N1–Ru–S1	167.61(15)
Ru–S(2)	2.233(17)	N1–Ru–S2	100.30(15)
Ru–Cl(1)	2.398(19)	N1–Ru–Cl2	89.33(14)
Ru–Cl(2)	2.404(19)	O1–Ru–Cl1	88.73(13)
		O1–Ru–S1	90.77(13)
		O1–Ru–S2	177.00(13)
		O1–Ru–Cl2	87.49(13)
		Cl1–Ru–S1	95.13(6)
		Cl1–Ru–S2	90.10(6)
		Cl1–Ru–Cl2	173.72(6)
		S1–Ru–S2	92.09(6)
		S1–Ru–Cl2	89.94(6)
		S2–Ru–Cl2	93.43(7)

S2 angle is $92.09(6)^\circ$. Thus, this report attests the proposed structure of $[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}(\text{HL}^1)(\text{DMSO})_2\text{Cl}_2]^{6a}$.

Analysis of crystal-packing of ligand-coordinated $\text{M}^{\text{II}}\text{Cl}_2$ -complexes in general^{14–16} of discrete and coordination polymer origin, including pyridine amide complexes¹⁶ is of special interest in our laboratory for identification of C–H \cdots Cl hydrogen-bonding interactions^{17,18}. As a part of our continued interest in various non-covalent interactions^{19–21}, careful analysis of the crystal packing of complex **1** reveals the presence of C–H \cdots O^{17a,18,20}, C–H \cdots Cl^{14–18} and C–H \cdots π ^{18,19,22} interactions (Table 3). The intermolecular C–H \cdots O contacts between one of the C–H of a methyl group of one of the coordinated DMSO molecule and O3 of the DMSO molecule of the neighbouring are present, leading to the formation of dimeric motifs via self-complementary hydrogen-bonding²³ (Fig. 3).

The methyl H of the second coordinated DMSO molecule is involved in C–H \cdots O interaction with the O2 of the other DMSO molecule of the neighbouring molecule resulting in the formation of a zig-zag 1D chain (Fig. 4).

One coordinated chloride ion (Cl2) is involved in C–H \cdots Cl hydrogen-bonding interaction (Fig. 5). The Cl2 forms hydrogen-bonding with the C–H of a methyl group of the second DMSO molecule, generating a 1D chain.

Also, a weak intermolecular C–H \cdots π ⁸ interaction gives rise to the 1D chain along c-axis (Fig. 6).

Complex **1** exhibits in acetonitrile a metal \rightarrow ligand charge-transfer (MLCT) transition at 455 nm, with molar extinction coefficient (ϵ) value of $2700 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. An additional ligand-centred transition is observed at 295 nm,

Fig. 3. View of the formation of a dimer via C–H \cdots O hydrogen-bonding in **1**. All the hydrogen atoms except those involved in hydrogen-bonding have been omitted for clarity.

Fig. 4. View of the formation of the 1D chain via C–H...O hydrogen-bonding in **1**. All the hydrogen atoms except those involved in hydrogen-bonding have been omitted for clarity.

Fig. 5. View of the formation of the 1D chain via C–H...Cl hydrogen-bonding in **1**. All the hydrogen atoms except those involved in hydrogen-bonding have been omitted for clarity.

Fig. 6. View of the formation of the 1D chain via C–H... π hydrogen-bonding in **1**. All the hydrogen atoms except those involved in hydrogen-bonding have been omitted for clarity.

Table 3. Non-covalent interaction parameters

D-H...A	H...A, Å	D...A, Å	D...H...A (°)
C15-H15B...O3	2.48	3.34(9)	149
C13-H13C...O2	2.42	3.32(7)	157
C14-H14B...Cl2	2.88	3.60(8)	133
C10-H10...π	3.11	3.85(17)	137

with ϵ value of $8000 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Fig. 7). Results are in correspondence with that reported in dichloroethane-methanol (4 : 1; v/v) mixture^{6a}.

Fig. 8. Cyclic voltammogram (100 mV/s) of a 1.0 mM solution of complex **1** at a Pt working electrode in acetonitrile (0.1 M in TBAP).

To investigate the possibility of identifying metal-centred redox, CV experiment on complex **1** was carried out (Fig. 8). The complex **1** undergoes in acetonitrile a one-electron reversible oxidation at 0.87 V vs SCE ($\Delta E_p = 80 \text{ mV}$), which is assigned as due to $\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}/\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}$ redox process. The reported value is 0.95 V vs SCE^{6a}. As in complex **1**, the ligand HL¹ is coordinated in its neutral form, so a dissociable N-H proton is present. To investigate the effect of deprotonation/protonation on the $E_{1/2}$ value of the $\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}/\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}$ redox-couple, we performed electrochemical titration (Fig. 9). Differential Pulse Voltammograms (DPV) were recorded for solutions of the complex **1** in acetonitrile, after progressive addition of stoichiometric equivalent of the base (Et_3N). It is observed that $\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}/\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}$ redox potential shifts to 420 mV cathodically, after addition of one equivalent of Et_3N . This result suggests that the deprotonation of the ligand stabilizes the trivalent state of Ru. Given this fact, it is reasonable to assume that deprotonation of N-H proton is accompanied by a donor atom switch over from pyridine and amide oxygen *N,O*-coordination to pyridine and deprotonated amide nitrogen *N,N*-coordination. To check reversibility of the protonation/deprotonation phenomenon, the titration was also done on this solution by addition of one equiv of acid (HClO_4). In fact, after addition of one equiv of HClO_4 to the one equiv of Et_3N added solution of complex **1**, the $\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}/\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}$ redox-process reverts back anodically by 420 mV and we observe the redox response at the same potential as that of original complex **1** (Fig. 9). Similar phenomenon of deprotonation at a remote site, has been observed for bis-ligand six-coordinate complexes of Fe^{III} ^{24a}, Ru^{II} ^{24b} and also for a mono-ligand four-coordinate Ni^{II} system^{24c}. The shift observed for $\text{M}^{\text{III}}/\text{M}^{\text{II}}$ redox potential values per N-H proton deprotonation is 345 mV, 335 mV and 248 mV, respectively. Compared to the bis-ligand complex of ruthenium(II)^{24b}, for complex **1** the corresponding shift is 420 mV, which is higher by 85 mV. We rationalize this result keeping in mind that in the present case the deprotonation is accompanied by amide *O* to strongly σ -donor deprotonated amide *N* donor site switch over, better stabilizing the Ru^{III} state.

Fig. 9. Differential pulse voltammograms (100 mV/s) of a 1.0 mM solution of complex **1** at a Pt working electrode in acetonitrile (0.1 M in TBAP).

Conclusion

A ruthenium(II) complex coordinated by a bidentate pyridine amide ligand in its neutral binding mode, two labile DMSO molecules and two chloride ions has been synthesized and structurally characterized. X-Ray structural characterization authenticates the structural identity of the complex. Extensive non-covalent interactions are present, as revealed from analysis of its crystal-packing. Cyclic voltammetric experiment reveals a reversible Ru^{III}/Ru^{II} redox-process, subject to protonation/deprotonation phenomenon. Careful acid-base titration experiments reveals donor atom switch over from amide *O* to deprotonated amide *N* coordination, accompanied by a cathodic potential shift of 420 mV of the Ru^{III}/Ru^{II} redox process. Notably, the proton-dependent redox process is reversible in nature. Studies on proof-of-concept of acid/base-dependent donor atom switch over of metal-coordinated pyridine amide ligands are currently underway and the outcome of such an investigation will be published elsewhere.

Acknowledgement

This work is supported by the Department of Science & Technology (DST), Government of India. RM sincerely thanks DST for a J. C. Bose Fellowship.

Supplementary data

Crystallographic data of the complex [Ru^{II}(HL¹)-(DMSO)₂Cl₂].4H₂O has been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center, CCDC number 1479447.

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